

The Stress and Coping Strategies among Senior Citizens Living in Old Age Home and with Family in New Delhi & NCR with a View to Develop and Disseminate Pamphlets on Stress Management: A Comparative study

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Abstract:- The last century has witnessed a rapid increase in the population of the senior citizens in the developed and industrialized countries. India ranks 4th in terms of absolute size of elderly population. In the above context, a study was conducted to understand the stress and coping strategies of the senior citizens residing in old age home and with family set up in New Delhi and NCR.

The objectives of the study were to compare the level of stress and coping strategies adopted among, to identify the relationship between stress and coping strategies among senior citizens living in old age home and with family, develop and disseminate pamphlets on stress management among senior citizens living in Old age home and with family in New Delhi and NCR. A total of 100 samples (50 senior citizens from old age home and 50 from with family) were selected by using convenient sampling technique. Settings of the study were an old age home and community setting. A structured interview rating scale was developed to determine the stress level and adopted coping strategies. The finding of the study revealed that majority of 60% senior citizens living in old age home were having mild stress and 70% senior citizens living with family were having moderate stress and no severe stress is there neither in old age home nor with family. The coping strategies used by senior citizens living with family, 84% were having poor coping strategies, 54% were having average coping strategies and 24% were using good coping strategies. The Pearson coefficient correlation was 0.1181 in between stress and coping strategies which was having significant relationship at the 0.05 level and 0.257 was coping strategies which was having significant relationship at the 0.05 level. The t-test value of stress among senior citizens was 3.39 which was having significant relationship at the level of 0.05 and t-test value of coping strategies among senior citizens was 8.935 which was significant at the level of 0.05. The study reflects that stress level was more among senior citizens living with family and coping strategies were used by senior citizens living in old age home.

I. INTRODUCTION

Today ageing is a concern world over. It is estimated that there are 416 million old age people (aged 65 yrs. and above) around the globe and by (2020)¹ worlds 11.9 % of population will be above 65 yrs. In India also the Trend is same, 7.5% of the total population is above 65 yrs. and the life expectancy is increasing gradually. In family they impact value and wisdom to the younger ones. They are the custodian to the younger one cultural and traditional wisdom and knowledge. They transfer it to the next generation. Old people are inevitable part of our prospectus society. Older people have different expectations these days about how they want to live. Many older people may want like to stay in their own home. It is about choice having the services in place to support them¹.

Older persons constitute one of the most vulnerable sections of the society. They are not only physically weak but also lack in economic resources, self-esteem and social status. Under the changing socio-economic and demographic conditions family is unable to provide support and care to the older persons and some are also feeling elderly are useless. Thus, old age put more wrinkle on one's mind than on his face. According to word of Seneca "Old age is an incurable disease". It cannot be prevented rather it can be protected and promoted. Globally older people constitute 11.7% in 2013 and the share of older persons aged >80 was 14%. Presently, about 2/3rd of the world's older persons live in developing countries. In India 7.5% population belong to age group above may projected to rise to 12.4% of population by the year 2026. There is sharp rise in age-specific death rate of 20/1000 persons in the age group of 60-64 years, 80 among 75- 79 years and 200 for the general characteristics of old age are physical and psychological changes which bring disabilities. They face number of problems such as dependency, ill health, absence of social security, loss of social role and recognition and non-availability of opportunities for creative use of leisure. With the advantage of the nuclear family, urbanization, influence of western culture and changes of lifestyle there is no space for elders in the family and may go for institutionalization. Separation from or loss of assistance

from their children makes them physically and emotionally neglected that lead to psychological problem like anxiety, depression, loneliness, feeling of insecurity, social isolation etc².

Today aging is a concern world over. Inadequate support from the care givers leads to lack of moral, emotional and physical support for senior citizens. The living condition of senior citizen differs in both developed and developing countries. When comparing the world scenario of Senior citizens population. India is not alone with respect to extremely rapid populating ageing among developing country³.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

A comparative study to assess the stress and coping strategies among senior citizens living in Old age home and with family in New Delhi & NCR with a view to develop and disseminate pamphlets on stress management.

➤ Aims of the Study

To assess the stress and coping strategies among senior citizens living in old age home and with family.

➤ Objectives

- To compare the level of stress among senior citizens living in old age home and with family in New Delhi and NCR.
- To compare the coping strategies adopted among senior citizens living in old age home and with family in New Delhi and NCR.
- To identify the correlation between stress and coping strategies among senior citizens living in old age home and with family in New Delhi and NCR.
- To develop and disseminate pamphlets on stress management among senior citizens living in Old age home and with family in New Delhi & NCR.

➤ Hypothesis

- H₁- There will be significant correlation between stress and coping strategies among senior citizens living in old age homes and with family in New Delhi NCR.
- H₂- There will be significant difference between Stress and Coping Strategies among senior citizens living in old age home and with family in New Delhi and NCR.
- H₃-There will be significant association between Stress among senior citizens living in old age home and with Family.
- H₄- There will be significant association between coping strategy among senior citizens living in old age home and with Family.

➤ Assumptions

- The Senior citizens those who are staying in old age home and with family may experience some level of stress.

- The senior citizens may adapt various coping strategies to help themselves to resolve uncomfortable feelings.
- The coping strategies adapted by the senior citizens living in old age home and with family may vary.

III. METHODOLOGY

➤ Research Approach-

The research approach used for the present study is quantitative approach.

➤ Resaerch Design-

The research design is comparative Survey research design.

➤ Variables Under Study

• Dependent variable:

Dependent variable in this study was stress and coping strategies adopted by the senior citizens.

• Independent Variable:

Independent variables in this study were background factors and place of living (Old age home and with family) of senior citizens.

➤ Setting of the Study-

Study was conducted in Tau Devi Lal Old age home, Faridabad and at Rural community of Makanpur, Indirapuram, Ghaziabad.

➤ Population-

The population included in the present study was the senior citizens both male and female living in selected old age home and with family in New Delhi and NCR above 65 years of age

➤ Sample-

The sample for present study comprised of 100 senior citizens above 65 years who were living in Tau Devi Lal old age home, Faridabad and Makanpur community, Indirapuram

➤ Sampling Technique-

Convenient sampling technique

➤ Sample Size-

The sample for the study consisted of 100 senior citizens (50 living in old age home and 50 living with family).

➤ Criteria for Selection of Sample

• Inclusion Criteria

- ✓ Senior Citizens above 65 years old
- ✓ Senior Citizens who are willing to participate in the study.
- ✓ Senior Citizens who are available at the time of data collection.

- ✓ Senior Citizens who have hearing capacity and able to verbalize their feelings.
- *Exclusion Criteria*
- ✓ Senior Citizens who cannot understand Hindi or English language.
- ✓ Senior Citizens who are mentally ill.

IV. DATA COLLECTION TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES

➤ *Part-1*

Part 1 is having two sub-parts, Part A includes Demographic variables and Part B consists of selected variables of Senior Citizens living in Old Age Home and with Family.

- *Part A:*
Demographic variables: It includes Age, Sex, religion, educational qualification, Previous Occupation, Marital Status, type of family, Number of Children.
- *Part B:*
Selected variables: it includes Residential status, Place of living, source of economic support, duration of staying in old age home (for those who are staying in institution), Reason of staying in institution and Habits.

➤ *Part-2*

Structured Interview schedule to assess the stress level experienced by the senior citizens.

There are total 36 items.

For positive statements- Each item scored -Always (2), Sometime (1), Never (0)

For negative statements- Each item scored -Always (0), Sometime (1), Never (2)

The area covered: Neglect by family members, depression, Social isolation, Anxiety

Table 1 Grading of Stress Interview Schedule

Stress Level	Marks	Percentage
Mild Stress	0-36	1-50%
Moderate Stress	37-53	51-75%
Severe Stress	54-72	76-100%

➤ *Part-3*

Structured interview schedule to assess the coping strategies

- There are total 36 items.
- Each item scored Never (0), Sometime (1), Always (2)
- The area covered: Cognitive Strategies, Recreational therapy, Prayer, social interaction.

➤ *Content Validity of Tool*

The content validity of the tool was established by 11 experts from the field of Psychiatry Psychology, Mental Health Nursing and Community Health Nursing. Out of them 1 expert from psychiatry, 1 expert from psychology, 3 experts from mental health nursing, 5 experts from community health nursing and 1 expert from social worker. Suggestions given by experts was incorporated in the tool and modified accordingly.

V. RESULTS

➤ *Section 1:*

- *Part A: Findings Related to Demographic Variables of Subjects*
- ✓ Majority of Samples were from age 65-70 years age that was 26 (52%) from Old age home settings and 33 (66%) were from senior citizens with family setting. 13 (26%) were from 71-80 years at old age home setting and 10 (20%) were from with family setting, 9 (18%) were from 81-90 years of age in Old age home setting and 5 (10%) were from with family setting, only 2 (4%) were from 90 above age group in both settings.
- ✓ Majority of the samples were Female that was 37 (74%) from Old age home setting and 41 (82%) were from with family setting.
- ✓ Majority of samples were any other Religion that was Sikh in 24 (48%) in Old Age Home setting and 39(78%) at with family setting were Hindu.
- ✓ Majority of samples at Old age home setting were illiterate that was 23 (46%) and 23 (46%) were Primary school at with family setting.
- ✓ Majority of samples were have their previous occupation in private sector in both settings. 27 (54%) from Old age home setting and 32 (64%) from with family setting.
- ✓ Majority of samples in Old age home setting were widow/widower that were 36 (72%) and with family setting 27 (54%) samples were married.
- ✓ Majority of samples were living in Nuclear family that were 39 (78%) in old age home setting and 29 (58%) with family setting.
- ✓ Majority of samples were having 3 children that were 17 (34%) in old age home setting and 23 (46%) of samples were having 2 children in with family setting.
- *Part B: Findings Related to Selected Variables of Subjects*
- ✓ Majority of the samples were having their own house that was 29 (58%) at with family setting.
- ✓ Majority of samples were living in Urban area in both setting that was 41 (82%) were in Old age home setting and 47 (94%) were from with family setting.
- ✓ Majority of samples were having source of economical support from social support that was 31 (62%) in old age home setting and 19 (38%) were taking from children in with family setting.
- ✓ Majority of samples were having 21 (42%) were living in old age home from one year of age.

- ✓ Majority of samples 47 (94%) were living in old age home because no children to take care.
- ✓ Majority of samples 47 (94%) were having no habit of abuse in old age home setting and in with family setting 13 (26%) were using smoking.

➤ Section 2:

- Findings Related to Assessment of Stress and Coping Strategies.

- ✓ Majority of stress among senior citizens who were living with family is high as compare to Old age home. 35 (70%) were having Moderate stress and 15 (30%) were having mild stress but no senior citizens were having severe stress.

- ✓ Majority of samples in Old age home setting were using coping strategies very well. 27 (54%) were having Average coping strategies and 12 (24%) were having good coping strategies.
- ✓ The mean of stress among senior citizens who were living old age home was 35.32, Median 34.5 and Standard Deviation was 4.9 and the mean of coping strategies was 32.86, Median 39.5 and Standard Deviation was 4.3 and the correlation was 0.1181 in between the stress and coping strategies.
- ✓ The mean of stress among senior citizens who were living with family was 38.92, Median 39.5 and Standard deviation 5.42 and coping strategies mean was 45.62, Median 39.5 and standard deviation.

Table 2 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Stress

Variables	Living in Old Age Home n ₁ =50		Living with Family n ₂ =50	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Mild stress	30	60%	15	30%
Moderate stress	20	40%	35	70%
Severe stress	0	0	0	0

Table 3 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Coping Strategies

Variables	Living in Old Age Home n ₁ =50		Living with Family n ₂ =50	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Poor Coping strategies	11	22%	42	84%
Average Coping Strategies	27	54%	8	16%
Good Coping strategies	12	24%	0	0

➤ Section 3:

- Comparison of Stress and Coping Strategies among Senior Citizens Living in Old Age Home and with Family

- ✓ The mean of stress among senior citizens living in Old Age home was 35.32, Median 34.5 and Standard Deviation was 4.9. The mean of stress among senior citizens living with family was 38.92, Median 39.5 and Standard Deviation was 5.42.
- ✓ The Mean of Coping Strategies among senior citizens living in Old Age Home was 32.86, Median 39.5 and Standard Deviation was 4.3. The Mean of Coping Strategies among senior citizens living with family was 45.62, Median 49 and Standard Deviation was 9.1.
- ✓ The t-Test of Stress was 3.39 among senior citizens living in Old age home and with family and t-Test of Coping Strategies was 8.935 among senior citizens living in old age home and with family.

Table 4 Mean, Median, Standard Deviation and Mean Difference of Stress Level and Coping Strategies of Senior Citizens Living in Old Age Home and with Family n=100

Variable	Senior Citizens Living in Old Age Home n ₁ =50			Senior Citizens Living with Family n ₂ =50			Mean Difference
	Mean	Median	SD	Mean	Median	SD	
Stress	35.32	34.5	4.9	38.92	39.5	5.42	3.60
Coping Strategies	32.86	32.5	4.3	45.62	49	9.1	12.76

Table 5 Comparison of Stress of Senior Citizens Living in Old Age Home and Senior Citizens Living with Family. n =100

	Mean	Median	SD	T-Test
Senior Citizens Living in Old Age Home	35.52	34.5	4.9	3.39*
Senior Citizens Living with Family	38.9	39.5	5.4	

(*) Significant at 0.05 level of significance.

➤ *Section 4:*

• *Correlation between Stress and Coping Strategies among Senior Citizens Living in Old Age Home and with Family*

- ✓ The mean of stress among senior citizens living in Old Age home was 35.32, Median 34.5 and Standard Deviation was 4.9. The mean of stress among senior citizens living with family was 38.92, Median 39.5 and Standard Deviation was 5.42.
- ✓ The Mean of Coping Strategies among senior citizens living in Old Age Home was 32.86, Median 39.5 and Standard Deviation was 4.3. The Mean of Coping Strategies among senior citizens living with family was 45.62, Median 49 and Standard Deviation was 9.1.
- ✓ The Pearson Correlation of Stress and Coping Strategies was 0.1181 among senior citizens living in Old age home and Pearson Correlation of Stress and Coping Strategies was 0.257 among senior citizens living with family.

Table 6 Correlation between Stress and Coping Strategies among Senior Citizen Living in Old Age Home

Variable	Mean	Median	SD	(r)
Stress	35.32	34.5	4.9	0.1181*
Coping Strategies	32.86	39.5	4.3	

(*) Significant at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 7 Correlation between Stress and Coping Strategies among Senior Citizens Living with Family

Variable	Mean	Median	SD	(r)
Stress	38.92	39.5	5.42	0.257*
Coping Strategies	45.62	49	9.1	

(*) Significant at 0.05 level of significance.

VI. DISCUSSION

The Discussion has been presented in context to the objectives and findings of the study conducted in context with the findings revealed by the other researchers.

Ageing is a natural process and it is considered as a normal biological and an inevitable process. The process of ageing is classically depicted as one of constant and inexorable decline after reaching a peak of bodily function & efficiency around the second decade of life⁴.

“Old age is an incurable disease”. But more recently Sir James sterling Ross commented “you do not heal old age, you protect it, you promote it and you extend it”. Aging is a major life change includes physiological & psychological changes. Old age should be regarded as a normal inevitable biological phenomenon. The aim of the current study to assess the stress and coping strategies among senior citizens living in old age home and with family. The present study revealed that the stress among senior citizens living with family is high as compare to senior citizens living in old age home and coping strategies were used by senior citizens living in old age home as compare to senior citizens living with family⁵.

The senior citizens living in Old age home 30 (60%) were having mild Stress and senior citizens living with family is 15(30%) were having mild stress. The senior citizens who were living in Old age home having 20 (40%) were having moderate stress and senior citizens living with family were 35 (70%) were having moderate stress.

The senior citizens living in Old age home were having good coping strategies 12 (24%) were having in senior citizens who were living in Old age home setting. The Senior citizens who were living in Old age home having 27 (54%) Average Coping strategies and with family setting 16% were having Average coping strategies. The senior citizens who were living in old age home 11(22%) were having poor coping strategies and senior citizens who were living with family having 42 (84%) poor coping strategies. Comparison of stress and coping strategies of senior citizens living in old age home and senior citizens living with family is significant at the level of 0.05. Correlation between stress and coping strategies among senior citizens living in old age home and with family is significant at the level of 0.05.

Similar findings were reported in a study conducted by Chakrabarti (2009)⁶ which showed that the stress level is high among senior citizens living with family as compare to senior citizens living in old age home assessed by the help of structured interview schedule with purposive sampling technique and snowball sampling technique.

Similar findings were reported in a study conducted by Anita R Met.al.,(2012)⁷. The study revealed that elderly living with family were overall (96.7%) of elderly had one or more stress problems as compare to the elderly living in old age home. The data was collected by interviewing them using a pre designed and pretested questionnaire as well as by clinical examination.

Therefore, the structured interview schedule was found effective to assess the stress and coping strategies among senior citizens living in old age home and senior citizens living with family.

VII. CONCLUSION

The conclusion drawn from the study is there is a significant correlation between stress and coping strategies among senior citizens between old age home and Family. There is a significant comparison between stress and coping strategies among senior citizens living in old age home and with family.

➤ *Ethical Considerations*

The ethical clearance was obtained from the Ethical committee of Holy Family Hospital, Tau Devi Lal Old age home, Faridabad and Legislative of Makanpur Community, Indirapuram, Ghaziabad. Formal administrative permission was taken from other institutions respectively. Written consent was obtained from the participants.

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